

The Influence of Nina F. Thornhill

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Abstract: Bhushan Gopaluni is a professor in the Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering at the University of British Columbia. He has known Prof. Nina Thornhill for nearly 20 years. Instead of writing a research article, this is a reminiscence on his interactions with Nina over these years.

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My first interactions with her were at the University of Alberta around 1999/2000 when I was a Ph.D. student. At that time, she was spending a sabbatical at the University of Alberta with Prof. Sirish Shah.

Around the same time, I happened to build a Matlab user interface for controlling level and temperature in a water tank. Prior to that we had analog controllers in the lab and

Matlab did not have a real time control software. I believe Nina just started working with Sirish and one of his Ph.D. students, Shoukat Choudhury, on topics such as data compression, valve stiction, spectral data analytics, performance assessment and so on. I helped Nina in the lab with the experiments. A quick search online brought up this paper by Nina, Sirish and Biao that was published in 2003:

CONTROLLER PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT IN SET POINT TRACKING AND REGULATORY CONTROL

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The first thing I noticed while working with Nina was the meticulous, sincere and serious approach she brought to research. She used to carry a thick notebook and took diligent notes during all our conversations. All her presentations used to be simply perfect.

Nina is certainly one of the few people that I have drawn tremendous inspiration from during my Ph.D. days.

Since then I met Nina at several conferences and closely followed her work on performance assessment, valve stiction analysis, causality analysis and a variety of other topics. She is simply one of the finest researchers in the world on any of the above topics.

Thank you, Nina for inspiring many younger generations of researchers and for the many lasting contributions you have made to process control and Chemical Engineering at large. I wish you all the success in this new phase of your life.